

EFFECT OF SPIRULINA POWDER TREATED MULBERRY LEAVES ON ECONOMIC TRAITS OF *Bombyx mori*

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Abstract

The present investigation entitled "Effect of spirulina powder treated mulberry leaves on economic traits of *Bombyx mori*" was carried out during 2024-2025 was undertaken with the objectives viz., to study the effect of spirulina powder on development of silkworm and to study the effect of spirulina powder on economic traits of silkworm. The experiment was conducted at Sericulture Laboratory, Department of Entomology, Dr. Panjabrao Deshmukh Krishi Vidyapeeth, Akola, during September to December 2024. The design used in the experiment was Completely Randomized Block Design with seven treatments and three replications. Treatments viz., T1 (0.5 gm spirulina powder solution), T2 (1.0 gm spirulina powder solution), T3 (1.5 gm spirulina powder solution), T4 (0.5 gm spirulina powder + 1% honey solution), T5 (1.0 gm spirulina powder + 1% honey solution), T6 (1.5 gm spirulina powder + 1% honey solution) and T7 untreated (control). During study it was observed that the treatment T6 (1.5 gm spirulina powder + 1% honey solution) found significantly superior over the others in case of single cocoon weight (1.92 g), shell weight (0.41 g), shell ratio (20.80), filament length (1046.6 m) and filament weight (0.33 g). In contrast, T₅ (1.0 gm spirulina powder + 1% honey solution) outperformed other treatment in case of denier (2.91).

Keywords: *Bombyx mori*, Silkworm, Honey, Economic Traits, Spirulina powder.

Introduction

The process of growing, breeding, management of silkworms to get pure raw silk is sericulture. The word Sericulture is derived from the Greek word 'sericos' meaning 'silk' and the English word 'culture' meaning 'rearing' (Bobade et al. 2019). Silk is known as "The Queen of Fibers" and because of its huge surface area and capacity for reproduction it offers microorganisms an ideal home. (Guangyu, Yan, Xiaoliang, & Yuyue, 2014). The lepidopteron economic insect known as the silkworm, *Bombyx mori* L. is well-known for producing mulberry silk. In our nation, the textile industry holds a special position. Sericulture is a very labour intensive, agro-based and lucrative economic activity. In conjunction with agriculture, sericulture is primarily performed by rural residents. Mulberry tree which are deciduous trees that grow wild and are also cultivated in many tropical and temperate regions of the world, are members of the family Moraceae of the genus *Morus*. Mulberry silkworms can easily digest and enjoy mulberry leaves. The leaves and young stems had protein contents ranging from 15% to 28%. There are nearly no harmful substances or anti-nutritional elements for mulberry silkworms, and the mineral content is higher. Currently, the total silk production in India is the highest among comparable agricultural crops.

The mulberry silkworm, *Bombyx mori* is a monophagous feeder on mulberry leaves and the nutritional quality has a great influence on the silkworm growth, silk yield and disease resistance (Ravikumar et al. 1988). Nutrition plays important role in improving growth and development of mulberry silkworm. It is stated that silk production is dependent on larval nutrition and nutritive value of mulberry leaves which plays effective role in producing good quality cocoons (Legay et al. 1958). Probiotics are the live microbial food supplements beneficially affecting host by improving microbial balance and

enhanced rapid cellular growth and development (Fuller et al. 1993). A hydrophobic structural protein called fibroin is present in silk, a protein-based biopolymer and is covered in a glue-like covering protein called sericin. Four types of silkworms are used to produce natural silk: the Eri silkworm (*Philosemiaricini*), the Muga silkworm (*Antheraea assamensis*), the Tasar silkworm (*Antheraea mylitta*) and the Mulberry silkworm (*Bombyx mori*). Mulberry silkworms prefer the mulberry plant. The mulberry plant is said to be indigenous to China or India especially the lower Himalayan slopes. Only the Bramhaputra Valley in India is home to (*Antheraea assamensis*) worldwide. The renowned muga silk is produced there (*Antheraea mylitta*), which lives in the thick forests of Bihar, Madhya Pradesh and Orissa produces tasar silk by feeding on (*Terminalia tomentosa*).

Materials and Methods

The present investigation was undertaken to study the effect of spirulina powder on the development and economic traits of silkworm hybrid FC₁ x FC₂ on V-1 variety of *Morus alba*. The investigation was undertaken during September 2024 to December 2024. The experiment was conducted at Sericulture Laboratory, Department of Entomology, Post Graduate Institute, Dr. Panjabrao Deshmukh Krishi Vidyapeeth, Akola. The design used in the experiment was Completely Randomized Block Design with seven treatments and three replications. The treatments details are shown in Table 1. Disease free laying of silkworm hybrid Fc₁ x Fc₂ procured from Central Sericulture Research & Training Institute, Mysore was used as test hybrid against mulberry variety V-1 as feed of silkworm, in present investigation the fresh mulberry leaves of V-1 variety were obtained from already established mulberry plantation at the field, Department of Entomology, Post Graduate Institute, Dr. Panjabrao Deshmukh Krishi Vidyapeeth, Akola.

Table 1: Treatment details

Treatments	Detail
T1	Feeding of mulberry leaves treated with spirulina powder 0.5 gm / 100 ml of distilled water.
T2	Feeding of mulberry leaves treated with spirulina powder 1.0 gm / 100 ml of distilled water.
T3	Feeding of mulberry leaves treated with spirulina powder 1.5 gm / 100 ml of distilled water.
T4	Feeding of mulberry leaves treated with spirulina powder 0.5 gm + 1% honey /100 ml of distilled water.
T5	Feeding of mulberry leaves treated with spirulina powder 1.0 gm + 1% honey /100 ml of distilled water.
T6	Feeding of mulberry leaves treated with spirulina powder 1.5 gm + 1% honey /100 ml of distilled water.
T7	Untreated

Rearing Method

In order to ensure homogeneous embryo growth, the disease-free layings (DFLs) of FC₁ X FC₂ bivoltine mulberry silkworms, which were acquired from Central Sericulture Research and Training Institute, Mysore were put in a black box, covered with a black piece

of fabric and left undisturbed for 48 hours. Mulberry plantations of V-1, which were well-grown were used as feed for the silkworm race. The enhanced silkworm rearing method suggested by Krishnaswami (1978) was applied in this investigation.

Method of recording observations:

Observation were taken in following parameters on ten randomly selected cocoon of silkworm hybrids from each replication of each treatment.

1 Single cocoon weight (g): The cocoon weight was recorded on 6th day of spinning. The averages of 10 cocoons were taken as single cocoon weight.

Weight of 10 cocoons

Single cocoon weight (g) = $\frac{\text{Weight of 10 cocoons}}{10}$

2 Single shell weight (g): The cocoon was cut open at one end and shell weight was recorded after removing pupae.

Weight of 10 shells

Single shell weight (g) = $\frac{\text{Weight of 10 shells}}{10}$

3 Cocoon shell ratio (%) : The cocoon shell ratio calculated as,

Single shell weight

Shell ratio (%) = $\frac{\text{Single shell weight}}{\text{Single cocoon weight}} \times 100$

Single cocoon weight

4 Cocoon filament length (m): Cocoon filament length was measured by reeling 10 cocoons in three replications with the help of epprouvate.

5 Cocoon filament weight (g): Cocoon filament weight was measured by weighing 10 cocoons in three replications with the help of electronic balance.

6 Denier: It is term used to denote the thickness of silk filament and expressed in terms of ratio of weight of filament, to the filament length multiplied by 9000.

Filament weight (g)

Denier = $\frac{\text{Filament weight (g)}}{\text{Filament length (m)}} \times 9000$

Filament length (m)

Results and Discussion

Cocoon weight (g):

The significantly highest single cocoon weight was observed in spirulina powder 1.5g + honey 1% (1.92 g). However, this treatment was found superior over the rest of other treatments. The next best treatment in terms of single cocoon weight was mulberry leaves treated with spirulina powder 1.0g + honey 1% (1.84 g), this treatment was found statistically at par with mulberry leaves treated with spirulina powder 0.5g + 1% honey (1.79 g). Followed by next treatment in terms of single cocoon weight with mulberry leaves treated with spirulina powder 1.5g (1.74 g), it was found statistically at par with mulberry leaves treated with spirulina powder 1.0g (1.68 g) and the lowest single cocoon weight was recorded in untreated mulberry leaves (1.60 g). Shruti et al. (2019) reported that cocoon weight was significantly higher in azolla (9.50 g) followed by soy milk, yeast and Spirulina (7.25 to 8.14 g). Anitha et al. (2015) recorded that the probiotic at two per cent concentration gave significant increase of cocoon weight (4.61 g) when compared with control (3.99 g) in eri silkworms. The results pertaining to yeast in the present study was supported by earlier works of Esaivani et al. (2014) where *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* treated MR2 mulberry leaves when fed to fifth instar *B. mori* larvae produced maximum cocoons weights (35.12 g/10) in five per cent concentration.

Single shell weight

Data revealed that the significant maximum shell weight was recorded in mulberry leaves treated with spirulina powder 1.5g + Honey 1% (0.41 g). However, this treatment was found statistically at par with mulberry leaves treated with spirulina powder 1.0g + 1% (0.40 g). Followed by next treatment in terms of single shell weight was mulberry leaves treated with spirulina powder 0.5g + Honey 1% (0.37 g), it was found statistically at par with mulberry leaves treated with spirulina powder 1.5g (0.36 g). Followed by next treatment in terms of single shell cocoon weight was recorded in treatment mulberry leaves treated with spirulina powder 1.0g (0.33 g), it was found statistically at par with mulberry leaves treated with spirulina powder 0.5g (0.32 g) and mulberry leaves with untreated (0.30 g). The present findings are correlate with Alagumanikumar et al. (2016) reported that the addition of honey in mulberry leaves significantly increase in shell weight.

Cocoon-shell ratio

Data revealed that the significant maximum cocoon-shell ratio was recorded in mulberry leaves treated with spirulina powder 1.5g + honey 1% (20.80 %) However, this treatment was found statistically at par with mulberry treated leaves with spirulina powder 1.0g + 1% honey (20.69 %). The next best treatment in terms of cocoon shell ratio was mulberry leaves treated with spirulina powder 0.5 g + 1% Honey (19.59 %). However, it was found statistically at par with mulberry leaves treated with spirulina powder 1.5g (19.16 %), mulberry leaves treated with spirulina powder 1.0 g (19.11 %). Followed by mulberry leaves treated with spirulina 0.5g (18.77 %), it was found statistically at par with mulberry leaves untreated (18.50 %). Tamilselvi et al. (2020) also observed that mulberry leaves enriched with honey showed significant increase in shell ratio. Kalokhe et al. (2024) reported that the effect of probiotics regarding shell ratio revealed that significant maximum shell ratio was recorded in Baker's yeast 1% (27.09 %) followed by spirulina powder 1.5% (23.78 %) and Baker's yeast 1.5% (23.49 %).

Cocoon filament length

Data revealed that the significant maximum cocoon filament length was recorded in mulberry leaves treated with spirulina powder 1.5g + honey 1% (1046.67 m) However, this treatment was statistically at par with mulberry leaves treated with spirulina powder 1.0g + 1% honey (987.00 m). The next best treatment in terms of cocoon filament length was mulberry leaves treated with spirulina powder 1.0 g (965.67 m). However, it was found statistically at par with mulberry leaves treated with spirulina powder 0.5g + 1% honey (942.67 m), mulberry leaves untreated (917.33 m) and mulberry leaves treated with spirulina powder 1.5g (888.67 m). Whereas the minimum cocoon filament length recorded in mulberry leaves treated with spirulina powder 0.5g (888.67 m). Findings of present investigation are quite close to Saad et al. (2014) who observed that camphor honey increased the silk filament length over the control. Khedr et al. also reported that increased silk filament length when silkworm larvae were supplemented with honey.

filament weight

Significantly maximum larval weight was recorded in mulberry leaves treated with Spirulina powder 1.5g + Honey 1% (0.33 g). However, this treatment was found statistically at par with mulberry leaves treated with spirulina powder 1.0g + 1% honey (0.32 g), the mulberry leaves treated with spirulina powder 0.5g + 1% honey (0.31 g). The next best treatment in terms of cocoon filament weight is mulberry leaves treated with spirulina powder 1.5g (0.30 g). Followed by next best in terms of cocoon filament weight is mulberry leaves treated with Spirulina powder 1.0g (0.27 g) it was found statistically at par with mulberry leaves untreated (0.26 g). The minimum weight of cocoon filament weight was recorded in mulberry leaves treated with spirulina powder 0.5g (0.23 g). The present findings regarding filament weight are correlate with Saad et al. (2014) who observed that the weight of silk filament increased when larvae fed on mulberry leaves treated with honey than control. Thulasi et al. (2015) who recorded that the positive impact honey on filament weight than the control. Shruti et al. (2019) reported that significant higher silk filament weight was recorded in the larvae reared on mulberry leaves supplemented with azolla (0.322 g) followed by soy milk, yeast and spirulina (0.234 to 0.290 g). The present findings regarding filament weight are correlate with Kalokhe et al. (2024) who observe that performance of Baker's yeast 1.5% (0.363 g) recorded significantly highest filament weight than Baker's yeast 1% (0.357 g).

Denier

Significantly maximum denier was recorded in mulberry leaves spirulina powder 1.0 g + 1% honey (2.91). However, this treatment was found statistically at par with mulberry leaves treated with spirulina powder 0.5g + 1% honey (2.90), mulberry leaves treated with spirulina powder 1.5g + 1% honey (2.89). Followed by mulberry leaves treated with spirulina powder 1.5g (2.68), mulberry leaves untreated (2.57), mulberry leaves treated with spirulina powder 1.0g (2.55). The lowest

denier was recorded in mulberry leaves treated with spirulina powder 0.5g (2.52). The present findings are in corroboration with the findings of Saad et al. (2014) who recorded significant increases in denier comparing control when larvae fed on mulberry leaves treated with camphor honey.

Conclusion

The study revealed that among all the seven treatments used, T6 i.e. (Spirulina powder 1.5g + 1% honey solution) showed the best results

for this single cocoon weight, single shell weight, shell ratio, filament length and filament weight. In case of denier the treatment T5 i.e. Spirulina powder 1.0g + 1% honey solution performed better over other treatments. It is concluded from the present investigation that T6 i.e. mulberry leaves treated with Spirulina powder 1.5g + 1% honey solution recorded a positive effect on development and economic parameters than untreated control batch.

Table 2: Effect of spirulina powder treated mulberry leaves on silkworm (*Bombyx mori*)

Treatment	Treatment details	Single cocoon weight (g)	Single shell wt (g)	Shell Ratio (%)	Filament Length (g)	Filament weight (g)	Denier
T1	Spirulina powder 0.5g	1.60	0.32	18.77(25.67)	888.67	0.23	2.52
T2	Spirulina powder 1.0g	1.68	0.33	19.11(25.92)	965.67	0.27	2.55
T3	Spirulina powder 1.5g	1.74	0.36	19.16(25.96)	905.33	0.30	2.68
T4	Spirulina powder 0.5g + Honey 1%	1.79	0.37	19.59(26.27)	942.67	0.31	2.90
T5	Spirulina powder 1.0g + Honey 1%	1.84	0.40	20.69(27.06)	987.00	0.32	2.91
T6	Spirulina powder 1.5g + Honey 1%	1.92	0.41	20.80(27.13)	1046.6	0.33	2.89
T7	Untreated	1.61	0.30	18.50(25.47)	917.33	0.26	2.57
	SE (m)±	0.02	0.01	0.20	22.18	0.01	0.05
	CD at 5%	0.07	0.03	0.60	67.27	0.02	0.15
	CV (%)	2.25	4.45	1.31	4.04	4.07	3.22

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